

Cross-cultural Universals: A Framework for Design Futures

Martyn Evans, School of Art & Design, University of Salford, United Kingdom, E: m.d.evans@salford.ac.uk, T: +44 (0)161 295 6159

Simon Sommerville, Department of Design, University of Central Lancashire, United Kingdom, E: srsommerville@uclan.ac.uk, T: +44 (0)1772 89 3343

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Abstract

Designers are required to research and develop products and services that will be desired by consumers. These proposals are often for a future where things that we take for granted today, may not be present in the form we currently understand or expect. The development of future products and services require designers to establish reference points that will transcend time. These reference points need to be as culturally universal as possible.

Key words

design futures, cross-cultural universals, forecasting, trends, semantic matrix, semantic mapping, cultural filter

Introduction

This paper (i) provides an overview of futures thinking and their relevance to design futures, (ii) identifies the relevance of cross cultural reference points or universals to contemporary design practice, and (iii) provides a framework for design futures that acknowledges the importance of cross-cultural universals.

The authors will argue that cross-cultural universals – practices, customs and beliefs found in all societies – such as family, housing, work, and status differentiation, influence aspects of future orientated products and services. Combined with established forecasting methods, cross-cultural universals provide a reference point that transcends a future time as they focus upon people - the constant in this activity. Understanding how people may behave in future scenarios is a powerful tool for designers. This understanding allows future products and services to be developed that will be not only required, but desired by the consumer. This empathy provides an opportunity for the designer to allow a level of emotional engagement to be created between a user a future product or service.

Futures Thinking

The seemingly relentless change in society, popular culture, technology, and consumer attitudes is of prime importance to contemporary design activity. An understanding of such change, and the drivers behind it, is of prime importance to designers. Without such an understanding, the success of products or services for a future context is seriously undermined. In a linear conception of time, the future is the portion of the timeline that is yet to occur; the past is the set of moments and events that have already occurred; and the present is the set of events that are unfolding.

A broad field of enquiry, futures studies explores, extrapolates, and portrays what the future could become from multiple perspectives. Futures studies takes as one of its important attributes the on-going effort to analyse images of the future to distinguish possible, probable and preferred futures. This approach has much to offer design as it provides a structured approach that reflects on how today's changes become tomorrow's reality. These changes may provide insights to broader as yet undefined shifts in culture and consumer behaviour (Fahey & Randall 1998, Lindgren & Bandhold 2003). Its proponents are, among other things, known as futurists, forecasters, futurologists, and foresight practitioners (Cornish 2004).

In today's rapidly changing world, many people believe that it is becoming almost impossible to plan for the future. We read everywhere about rapid and constant change and, therefore, the increasing unpredictability of the future. The common feature is that the future is uncertain. This does not mean that we should not attempt to prepare for the future, on the contrary, we should engage fully with activities that allow us to prepare for the non-preparable. Through this engagement we may be able to identify and develop strategies that allow organisations to consider how they may be an integral element of such futures (Coughlan & Prokopoff, 2004; Lindgren & Bandhold, 2003).

Bevolo argues that the future seems more complicated and more difficult than ever to forecast, yet people feel the urge, more than ever before, to know what lies ahead. It is of key importance for companies to satisfy this need by exploring the future and in this way remaining at the cutting edge and maintaining credibility and leadership (Bevolo 2002).

Design Futures: Key Concepts

Design utilises future orientated approaches to explore the context of the outputs of its endeavours. Design Futures – the term associated with future orientated design activity, is a catch all phrase that brings together the numerous approaches available to design practice when consideration of the future is the primary goal. The following is a summary of key futures concepts pertinent to design activity (Vanston 2003, Jonas 2001, Woodhuysen 1990, Evans 2004, Fahey & Randall 1998, Sommerville & Evans 2006, Power & Tangsantikul 2005):

<p>Horizon Scanning - Includes techniques such as environmental scanning, monitoring, and tracking for identifying, emerging trends and events of importance to an organisation. They vary in purpose, focus and utilisation. Consideration needs to be given to ‘external’ information from the widest range of media combined with ‘internal’ industry specific information</p>
<p>Forecasting - A forecast is a simple or complex look at the qualities and probabilities of a future event or trend. There is a differentiation between a forecast, which is generally not point-specific to time or place, and a prediction, a specific, usually quantitative statement about some future outcome. Forecasting seeks to anticipate the future on the basis of historical and current knowledge and trends</p>
<p>Backcasting - Forecast an event that will occur in the future and then ask the question ‘How did this event come to be...?’ The task is then to develop a scenario (or series of events) to explain how the proposed future might actually come about. Backcasting offers a way to get a group to envision a desirable future and then determine what must happen in order for the goal to be reached</p>
<p>Trends - A general direction in which something is developing or changing. A trend is something that represents a deeper change than a fad; longer term and deeper socio-dynamic forces. By definition a trend has already begun – its existence implies that it already has an inclination. A trend is spotted rather than created. Trends come in all sizes. A mega-trend may describe complex interactions between many factors and may extend over many generations</p>
<p>Scenarios - A descriptive vision of the future communicated by a narrative; a description of a sequence of events that might possible occur in the future. This is an extremely useful approach for design activity as it allows a simple or complex consideration of the future. In brief, a scenario is normally developed by: (i) studying the facts of a situation, (ii) selecting something that might happen, and (iii) imagining the various ways for that development to occur and the sequence of events that it might follow. This process helps to communicate the essence of a design idea within its probable context of use</p>

Table 1. Design Futures: Key Concepts

Kevin McCullagh, director of Seymour Powell Foresight, the research arm of the leading UK product design consultancy describes the role of the ‘design/future’ interface as, the system for integrating the examination of economic, social, cultural and technological futures into the design process. He advocates an action-orientated vision of the future, which informs design strategy, rather than a detached conjecture about (or prediction of) the future. This approach requires a core set of multidisciplinary competences that includes sociology, technological insight, user research and marketing and of course, design. Distilling a diverse mass of data (mood boards, statistics, ethnographic research, scenario plans, etc.), the results of months of research, into a format that both the clients, who are paying for the service, and the designers, who will have to convert these recommendations into products, can understand and are willing to embrace is no mean feat (Ward 2002).

During his time at Fitch, Woudhuysen describes his perspective of design futures - gathering information so that they can get a clear idea of the future, is something that is essential for design to provide strategic advantage. Utilising three research strands, Fitch consider the following areas central to design futures (Woudhuysen, 1992):

<p>Commercial Information – understanding the industry, its sectors, trade shows, exhibitions, market reports, etc. Likely economic trends in countries are observed as this highlights potential market developments. Understanding which countries are going to ‘do the business in design’, it is important to keep trends in international relations under the microscope</p>
<p>Design Information – library of materials and samples. This information helps designers specify materials, colours, textures, etc. Trends are predicted for identified periods – 1 year, 2 years, etc. Associational words are also used to summarise potential trends</p>
<p>Visual Information – in the design press, at product launches, trade fairs, in books, magazines and the output of numerous design groups. This information allows an informed overview of current developments to be reviewed.</p>

Table 2. Information Sources for Design Futures

Woudhuysen adds... ‘The working methods of the Information Group (at Fitch) are largely analytical, but also very synthetic. We like to put together a number of different perspectives. We are also very idealistic – although we like to quantify, although we are interested in economics, we think that intuition, metaphor and these sorts of emotional issues are, and must

remain, very important to design. Aesthetic, stylistic or intuitive issues are very important for us to consider. And finally we are also pragmatic. The Information Group know what its about and know what the future is going to be.’ (Woudhuysen, 1992)

Behaviour is influenced by the space that we occupy – location and context are key influences on how we behave and interact with each other, organisations, brands and products. Exploring this can help us understand how and why people spend their time across different spaces. This can produce a rich picture of lifestyles and explain influences upon consumer wants and desires. This is of key importance to design activity as a clear understanding of how people behave in the present, informs the multitude of ways they could behave in the future. Design must consider the potential behaviours of future consumers in future contexts. To do this they need approaches that assist in their creative process. McCullagh states that the idea of knowing about the products that today’s consumers have been exposed to – and may have bought or aspired to buy in the recent past – will, especially when aligned to an analysis of recent design trends, give a more nuanced insight into both the aesthetics of popular culture and the realities of consumer buying habits (Ward 2002).

Many of the approaches of design futures, require designers to undertake the creative ‘imagineering’ of future scenarios populated by attitudes, behaviours, needs, wants and aspirations. Dealing with the various possible, probable and potential future states is challenging. With no foolproof methods at their fingertips, design is continually evolving ways of addressing these issues. The constant in these futures is human beings. The following section will outline how humans and their associated behaviour can be assistive in the consideration of future orientated design activities.

Cross-cultural Universals and Design Futures

Cross-cultural universals – practices, customs and beliefs found in all societies – such as family, housing, work, and status differentiation provide reference points to our world and the way we live in it (Fox 2005). By definition, Cross-cultural universals are immutable, representing as they do, basic aspects or characteristics of human existence. These universals are embedded in our societies, and contribute to the fabric of our very existence.

Cross-cultural universals are not static, they change over time. For example, the role of the family in our modern day society is very different to its role several generations ago. The

concept of the family has received much attention in modern times, and this is something that is unlikely to change. What the family means to society, and the way that it engages with this concept, is something that will be with us well into the future. The question of what the family may become is open to much debate. Here we expose an important point: the family will be around in the future but its make up may be very different to how it is in the present, or how it was in the past. Acknowledging that there will be inevitable change allows possible, probable and potential future states to be considered.

Truch and Hulme argue that an individual's set of social identities tend to be presented within the framework of roles that are played, e.g. mother, manager, friend, artist, etc. The segmentation of roles along the time axis have traditionally been linear and unitary. Within each time segment, usually attached to a particular location, a single role is played and displayed. A change in role is often associated with a change of location (Truch & Hulme 2004).

Cross-cultural universals have been utilised in design futures activities by a number of organisations. The following examples outline the relevance and importance of this approach:

During their 'Visions of the Future' design futures exploration, Philips undertook a wide ranging future orientated design undertaking in the form of over 300 scenarios based on the socio-cultural and technological research. These scenarios (short stories describing a product concept and its use) utilised five basic parameters: people, time, space, objects and circumstances. In view of the extensive nature of the project, further grouping was necessary to break this wide scope down into more manageable pieces. A simple structure, focusing on people rather than technological categories, was used to represent all aspects of everyday life - the four 'domains' - Personal, Domestic, Public and Work, and Mobile (Marzano 1996).

Whilst Philip's 'Visions of the Future' project looked to consider cross-cultural universals as a starting point for a number of forecasted product scenarios, they were careful to be specific in terms of their target markets. Described by inference as 'first world', the clear inference was that whilst, cross-cultural universals are constant, their interpretation and subsequent manifestation within a cultural situation are not. Marzano elaborates 'We could not hope to gain a complete picture of what people will need in the many diverse societies around the world. We therefore looked at socio-cultural developments only in societies which lead in the

adoption of new technologies, such as North America, Europe, Japan and Australasia' (Marzano 1996). Clearly, for the designer, proposing a concept for an as yet to exist market is problematic and is analogous to designing a current day product for a market that an individual has no direct knowledge of. Subtleties of usage or formatic nuances may be lost or misinterpreted, potentially with disastrous consequences for the products ultimate success.

In "The Delphi Project' Philips focussed on: (i) the exploration and understanding of possible human futures, and (ii) the understanding of what might makes life better for different people and different cultures. The specific questions considered include: What will the world look like in the future? What values do people hold now, both as members of a society and as individuals? What values and attitudes do different generations hold? How might the world and all its different societies and ages change? How might it develop and refine itself and its beliefs and desires? The insights gained help Philips to create meaningful innovations and branding and business strategies. Cross-cultural universals were considered to be central to the project activities (www.design.philips.com, 2005a).

In all human societies, food is surrounded by social and personal rituals that are deeply embedded in our culture. Today, the pleasures of mealtimes can help us to compensate for the rushed pace and complexity of our lives. In the Culinary Art project, a multidisciplinary team from Philips Design, together with experts from Philips Domestic Appliances, took a fresh look at the way we currently prepare, eat and serve food, and how we may be doing it in the near future. Based on an analysis of lifestyle trends, the project applies new digital technologies to create potential new appliances and settings so that people can enjoy traditional benefits and experiences within their fuller, faster and more varied lifestyles (www.design.philips.com, 2005b).

By considering a series of forecasted propositions, based on cultural variance regarding a cross-cultural universal, a range of slanted, or tailored, final scenarios can be developed to target different cultural groups regarding the final proposed scene. Alternatively, a singled finished scenario might be tested against a number of alternative 'cultural' drivers that in themselves represent modifying aspects regarding the final interpretation of the given scene.

In 'A Foresight Saga', the work of UK design consultancy Seymour Powell's futures wing Seymour Powell Foresight (SPF) is explored, with reference to their work with the Korean

electronics manufacturer Samsung. The company's requirement was to build on their initial understanding of European design tastes and to define a model of European design culture, to assist in future product development. SPF began by developing a series of national 'cultural basements' – collections of images that represented the historical references that defined a nation's visual culture. The rationale being that knowledge of what today's buying audience had been exposed to and also possibly aspired to in the recent past, might allow a more subtle interpretation of future aesthetic developments. This activity was then developed to define possible trajectories that pervading aesthetic trends might take or lead to (Ward 2002).

To base the exploration on a strongly visual level, rather than a statistical model is of note for the recognition of an existing national market 'taste' and the need to first understand it before attempting to extrapolate it primarily in aesthetic rather than functional terms.

This approach identifies two issues that are worth considering further. Firstly, that cultural background has an effect on the direction or nature of a product – this also appears to be based on an historical reference. Secondly, that the concepts were based on an aesthetic reference – in these terms a far more explicit strategy in terms of provoking an emotive response from a target audience based on an inferred conscious/ subconscious contextualisation.

It is too simplistic to consider a cultural difference, purely as a result of geographic location. A larger, 'national' cultural profile is the composite result of an almost unimaginable number of lower level, more subtle cultural profiles that exist within the larger grouping. It is relatively easy to understand, or recognise the cultural differences between two individuals from North America and Far East Asia, even if these are stereotypical, or 'shallow surface' differences. However, there may be as a significant difference between two teenagers passing each other in a street – one might be a sport orientated 'jock', the other an authority hating 'cyberpunk'. Culturally, they may be further apart than the two individuals from each side of the planet. Ironically, given the prevalence of communication and media technology nowadays, two 'cyberpunk' teenagers from North America and Asia might see themselves existing in a shared culture. This is their cross-cultural universal thread, off of which their cultural structure is constructed.

Most of us do not span radically different cultures in most of our day-to-day activities. Our values derive from the interplay between the norms of culture we were reared in and our

awareness of a larger, newer world that calls to our sense of concern. To say that we derive our sense of morality from the culture we were reared in is to admit a vast panoply of influences, given the range of texts we may have been exposed to in our formal education and the range of stories we have internalised from years of television and movies (Schwartz 2004).

Scenarios should always include the influence that the pervading culture has on peoples values – particularly the culture of large generations of people. Schwartz details that there used to be four ways of living in America – poverty, working class, middle class, or upper class. But now the common experiences of ‘baby boomers’ have been transformed through their own experimentation, into an amazing diversity of lifestyles. Steve Barnett in a GBN meeting described people who are ‘bankers by day and punkers by night’ – comfortably moving between discontinuous lifestyles. Advertisers and employers can no longer look at markets and workforces as simple and consistent. (Schwartz 2004)

Cross-cultural Universals and the Design Futures Framework

As already identified, the potential use of cross-cultural universals to support design futures undertakings is complex and requires a broad understanding of numerous issues. The incorporation of cross-cultural universals within the design activity requires a flexibly structured approach while acknowledging that a single ‘one size fits all’ strategy is not universally appropriate. The authors propose the following as an outline framework that supports design futures activities. It should act as a guide rather than a rigid structure that must be adhered to.

Scenarios: The use of scenarios are central to the development, exploration and communication of an overall context of possible, probable and preferred futures. It proves to be an effective mechanism for design activity as it allows a simple or complex consideration of the future. Widely used in various guises, scenarios can be seen as a starting point for design futures activities. Scenarios can utilise ‘mega-trends’ as an integral part of their development.

Cultural Ethnography: A development of traditional ethnography, it utilises digital technology including photo journals and video dairies. Here the aim is to understand the nuances imbedded in particular cultures to provide the development team with rich insights. These insights are particularly useful when referenced across a number of cultures as they provide the opportunity to identify ‘universality’ regarding needs, wants and desires.

Semantic Matrix: A visual representation tool - allows the relative measure of cultural ‘universality’. It provides an accessible and highly adaptable method for design futures activities as the number of ‘nodes’ upon the matrix, along with the ‘values’ attached to each node can be revised and adapted for each undertaking. Useful when individual concepts needs to be explored but also appropriate when a number of concepts have been developed and thus allows comparison across the concept activity.

Semantic Dimensions: There are two kinds of semantic dimensions. One is defined in terms of *polar opposite scales*, for example:

good	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	bad
strong	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	weak
fast	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	slow

The other kind is defined in terms of *feature scales*, which are scales that express the degree to which an attribute is present and go from ‘complete absence’ (zero) to ‘fully present’; for example:

0	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	post-modern
0	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	craftsmanship
0	:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:_:	voluminous

Combinations of semantic dimensions can be used to explore and/or compare ‘universality’ of aspects of design concepts. This is normally utilised when a number of concepts have been established thus utilised in the latter stages of idea generation.

Semantic Mapping (or cross-hair mapping): A versatile template normally presented as a grid, comprising four sections. This is a particularly appropriate when a number of concepts need to be mapped against each other. The ‘values’ upon the grid can be changed allowing various cultural aspects of concepts to be compared and explored.

Table 3. Design Futures Framework

We can see that a relatively simple framework for the inclusion of cross-cultural universals in design futures activities provides an endless series of potential approaches. To put this simply, this cross-cultural framework is adaptable and customisable to particular project

requirements. Each element of the framework is particularly effective at specific points in the development timeline, however their selection and utilisation must be considered carefully, whether this be at the beginning, middle or end of a futures activity.

The designer must consider, based on the creative objectives of the activity where in the activity cultural referencing is to be used and whether it is ultimately to be used as a driver during the early stages of the activity or a filter towards the latter stages of the process.

Concluding Remarks

Clearly there exists a relationship between cross cultural universals, cultural background and the interpretation of futures based scenarios. Whilst a cross cultural universal can provide a 'bridge' into an envisaged future situation, regarding a viewers understanding and willingness to consider a possibility, the cultural profile of the viewer will fundamentally effect that interpretation in a way that the designer will not necessarily see themselves.

This paper has considered the complex interplay of cultural universals and the design futures activity. These challenging areas do not readily provide clear and conclusive solutions. The authors recognise this and have attempted to provide a broad and adaptable framework that provides design with a structural basis for engaging with cross-cultural universals in a design futures context.

In an attempt to convey the interdependent relationship of a time frame (past, present and future), cultural references, and futuring activity (scenarios and context), the authors propose the following 'Cultural Filter'. It supports their position that cultural reference points are central to successful design futures undertakings. Cross-cultural universals inform the designers activity providing as they do, insights into consumer lifestyles, needs, wants and desires.

Figure 1. Cultural Filter

The diagram recognises the basic interrelationship between an individual, their past, a future, described as a scenario and the context that the future scenario is placed within.

Whilst a cross cultural universal may extend though past, present and future, the subtlety of its manifestation in the mind of the viewer will be fundamentally shaped, either directly, or indirectly by the pervading cultural environment the individual exists within. This personalisation cannot be guessed by the designer, however it can provide opportunities for the designer to discover subtleties of interpretation or wish that can additionally aid the definition or refinement of a futures scenario or 'blue sky' concept activity.

The authors intend to further explore and test their initial proposal by directly applying the techniques discussed in this paper to a series of forecast activities in order to more fully develop an understanding of the effect and range of cross cultural universality.

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